

ANALYTICAL TOOLS FOR PROFITABILITY ASSESSMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13885691>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisdagi asosiy e'tibor O'zbekiston tijorat banki sektorida rentabellikni baholash uchun mo'ljallangan tahliliy metodologiyalarni tekshirish va baholashga qaratilgan. Tijorat banklarida rentabellikni baholash moliyaviy natijalarni har tomonlama tahlil qilishni nazarda tutadi. U moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlarning turli jihatlarini yoritib, yangi nisbatlar va dekompozitsiyalarni taqdim etadi. Turli metodologiya va yondashuvlarni sinchiklab o'rganib, tadqiqot O'zbekiston bozorida faoliyat yuritayotgan banklarning moliyaviy faoliyatini baholashda ushbu vositalarning samaradorligi va qo'llanilishi haqida tushuncha berishga qaratilgan. Keng qamrovli tahlil va empirik tadqiqotlar orqali tadqiqot O'zbekiston bank sektori rentabelligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni chuqurroq tushunishga hissa qo'shishga intiladi va shu orqali soha manfaatdor tomonlar, siyosatchilar va tadqiqotchilar uchun qimmatli natijalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ROA, ROE, CAR, Bank kapitali, depozit, kreditlash, risk, rentabellik, moliyaviy hisobot tahlili.

Abstract. The article focuses on the examination and evaluation of analytical methodologies tailored for assessing profitability within the commercial banking sector of Uzbekistan. Profitability assessment in commercial banks involves a comprehensive analysis of financial performance. It introduces novel ratios and decompositions, shedding light on various aspects of financial performance. By scrutinizing various methodologies and approaches, the research aims to provide insights into the effectiveness and applicability of these tools in assessing the financial performance of banks operating within the Uzbekistan market. Through comprehensive analysis and empirical investigation, the study endeavors to contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing profitability in the banking sector of Uzbekistan, thereby offering valuable implications for industry stakeholders, policymakers, and researchers.

Keywords: ROA, ROE, CAR, Bank Capital, Deposit, Lending, Risk, Profitability, financial statement analysis.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена рассмотрению и оценке аналитических методологий, предназначенных для оценки прибыльности коммерческого банковского сектора Узбекистана. Оценка рентабельности коммерческих банков предполагает комплексный анализ финансовых показателей. В нем представлены новые коэффициенты и разложения, проливающие свет на различные аспекты финансовых показателей. Путем тщательного изучения различных методологий и подходов исследование направлено на предоставление информации об эффективности и применимости этих инструментов при оценке финансовых показателей банков, работающих на рынке Узбекистана. Посредством всестороннего анализа и эмпирических исследований исследование призвано способствовать более глубокому пониманию факторов, влияющих на прибыльность банковского сектора Узбекистана, тем самым предлагая ценные выводы для заинтересованных сторон отрасли, политиков и исследователей.

Ключевые слова: ROA, ROE, CAR, банковский капитал, депозит, кредитование, риск, рентабельность, анализ финансовой отчетности.

The profitability of a commercial bank is an important factor to measure its comprehensive development level. As an important part of Uzbekistan's financial system, commercial banks fully play the four major functions of credit intermediary, payment intermediary, economic regulation and financial services and play a vital role in the stable development of the national economy and the optimal allocation of resources. However, with the continuous advancement of Uzbekistan's interest rate marketization, the risks faced by commercial banks have gradually increased and the uncertainty of interest rate fluctuations has made competition among commercial banks more intense. At the same time, a series of factors such as the prosperity and development of the Internet financial industry and the increasingly open financial market are severely impacting the development of traditional physical banking. Commercial banks must have more advanced management systems and efficient asset utilization in order to invincible in the fierce market competition. Profit maximization is one of most important objectives of commercial banks because survive and face competition in competitive business environment at long term. How to accurately measure the profitability of the bank, to achieve the increase of shareholder wealth and the sustainable operation of the bank, is of great significance to the entire financial market. There are several analytical tools available for profitability assessment, each offering unique insights into different aspects of a business's financial performance. By leveraging these analytical tools effectively, banks can identify strengths and weaknesses in their operations, capitalize on opportunities for growth, and navigate challenges with confidence and agility. The profitability indicators of the Banking system of Uzbekistan are presented in the table below.

Profitability indicators of banking sector

	<i>In billion UZS</i>	
Income and expenses of the banking system	01.09.2023 y.	01.09.2024 y.
Interest income	54,831	71,854
Interest expenses	36,189	50,131
Interest margin	18,642	21,723
Non-interest income	27,640	33,992
Non-interest expense	7,660	14,148
Operating expenses	12,028	14,346
Non-interest income (loss)	7,952	5,499
Allowance for probable loan and leases losses	14,319	13,789
Evaluation of non-credit losses	3,573	4,304

Net profit (Loss) before Tax	8,702	9,128
Expense regarding income tax	2,098	1,919
Net profit (loss)	6,604	7,209
Profitability indicators of the banking system		
Return on assets (ROA)	2.3	2.0
Return on equity (ROE)	11.8	10.6
Ratio of net interest income to total assets	4.6	4.5
Ratio of net interest income from loans to total loans	6.3	6.4
Ratio of net interest income to total liabilities	5.3	5.2
Ratio of net interest margin to total assets	4.9	4.8

In this thesis, we delve into the realm of analytical tools utilized by commercial banks to assess profitability, focusing on key metrics such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), capital adequacy ratio (CAR), and their implications for deposit management, lending practices, and risk mitigation strategies. Through comprehensive financial statement analysis and strategic insights, banks can unlock new avenues for maximizing profitability while ensuring long-term viability and resilience. Return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) are fundamental metrics used by commercial banks to gauge their profitability and operational efficiency. ROA measures the bank's ability to generate profits from its assets, indicating how effectively management utilizes its resources to generate earnings: $\text{Return on Assets (ROA)} = \text{Net profit} \div \text{Average Total Assets}$. Net profit can be found from a company's statement of profit or loss, and assets are found on its balance sheet. On the other hand, ROE assesses the profitability of the bank from the perspective of shareholders' equity, reflecting the return earned on shareholders' investment: $\text{ROE} = \text{Net profit} / \text{Shareholders' Equity}$. ROE provides a simple metric for evaluating investment returns. Analyzing ROA and ROE provides insights into the bank's performance relative to industry peers and historical trends. A high ROA and ROE indicate efficient asset utilization and strong profitability, whereas declining ratios may signal operational inefficiencies or heightened risks. Commercial banks employ financial statement analysis techniques to dissect the components of ROA and ROE, identifying drivers of profitability and areas for improvement. Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is a critical measure of a bank's financial health and resilience, representing the proportion of a bank's capital to its risk-weighted assets: $\text{CAR} = (\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital}) \div \text{Risk-weighted assets}$. Adequate capitalization is essential for banks to absorb losses, maintain depositor confidence, and comply with regulatory requirements. By analyzing CAR, banks assess their capacity to withstand adverse shocks and sustain lending activities while safeguarding depositors' interests. Bank capital serves as a buffer against unexpected losses and provides a foundation for prudent risk-taking and growth. Capital management strategies, such as capital allocation

and capital optimization, play a pivotal role in enhancing profitability while maintaining regulatory compliance. Banks employ stress testing and scenario analysis to evaluate the impact of adverse events on capital adequacy and develop contingency plans to mitigate risks. Deposit management and lending practices are integral components of profitability assessment for commercial banks. Deposits serve as a primary source of funding for banks, enabling them to finance lending activities and generate interest income. Effective deposit management involves optimizing the mix of interest-bearing and non-interest-bearing deposits, minimizing funding costs, and maximizing net interest margin (NIM). Lending practices directly impact the profitability and risk profile of commercial banks. Banks evaluate creditworthiness, loan pricing, and collateral requirements to mitigate credit risk and enhance loan profitability. By employing risk-adjusted pricing models and credit scoring techniques, banks tailor lending strategies to different customer segments, optimizing risk-return tradeoffs and maximizing portfolio profitability. Risk management plays a pivotal role in profitability assessment for commercial banks, as the pursuit of profitability must be balanced with prudent risk-taking and mitigation strategies. Banks face various risks, including credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, and operational risk, which can impact profitability and financial stability. Financial statement analysis enables banks to identify and quantify risks, assess their impact on profitability, and develop risk management strategies to mitigate adverse outcomes. Banks employ risk measurement techniques such as value-at-risk (VaR), stress testing, and scenario analysis to evaluate the potential impact of adverse events on profitability and develop contingency plans to mitigate risks.

In conclusion, analytical tools are indispensable for profitability assessment in commercial banks, enabling them to optimize financial performance, mitigate risks, and enhance shareholder value. By analyzing key metrics such as ROA, ROE, CAR, and employing financial statement analysis techniques, banks gain valuable insights into their profitability drivers and areas for improvement. Deposit management, lending practices, and risk management strategies play a pivotal role in maximizing profitability while ensuring long-term viability and resilience in today's dynamic banking landscape. As banks continue to innovate and adapt to evolving market conditions, the importance of analytical tools in profitability assessment will only continue to grow, shaping the future of banking for years to come.

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